

Circular Steel for Mass Market Applications

INTRODUCING SCRAP-BASED ELECTRIC ARC FURNACE STEEL IN MASS-MARKET SHEET METAL GOODS

CiSMA aims to introduce **100% scrap-based Electric Arc Furnace (EAF)** steel products into mass-market steel sheet consumer goods, currently manufactured through the integrated Blast Furnace – Basic Oxygen Converter route.

The project will help **cut CO₂ emissions**, boost **circular economy** and reduce **EU's foreign dependency** on critical raw materials in key European.

CiSMA will tackle the challenge of unwanted trace elements in scrap that affect steel quality, focusing on how residual elements like copper interact with base steel.

With a toolbox of test methodologies and Machine Learning (ML)-enhanced modelling tools, CiSMA will enable the integration of recycled EAF steel in components from the **automotive and commercial laundry solutions industries**.

Start-end date
1 November 2024 - 30 April 2028

Duration
42 months

Budget
4,4M€, 100% funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme

PROJECT APPROACH

EAF-based, scrap-intensive steelmaking

Advanced characterisation through synchrotron and Atom Probe Tomography to design steel grades and determine safe residual thresholds

Scrap analysis and improvement

Analysing end-of-life scrap quality and improving the steel stream using automatic separation

Novel tests and enabling tools

- Rapid fracture toughness tests
- Fast forming embrittlement tests
- Fatigue tests
- ML-enhanced online tests to measure formability
- Data-driven modelling and digital twins

Four EAF scrap-based sheet steel products

1 High-formability steel	1 Interstitial-free steel	2 High-strength steels
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Two mass-market use cases

Demonstrating the 100% recycled steels in mass-market products from Volvo Cars and Electrolux Professional

CiSMA ambition is to develop 100% scrap-based EAF steel products and introduce greener solutions for mass-market steel sheet consumer goods to contribute to a circular economy in the European steel industry.

CONSORTIUM:

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